

A STUDY ABOUT STRESSED ASSETS MANAGEMENT OF SOUTH INDIAN BANK

¹Dr. Faraz Ahmad

¹Assistant Professor, Amity School of Economics, Amity University, Gurugram, Haryana, India

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7092-1484>

Email: ahmad_faraz@rediffmail.com

²Divyakshi Singh

Masters Student in Economics, Amity School of Economics, Amity University, Gurugram, Haryana, India

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0028-0486>

Email: divyakshisingh012@gmail.com

Article History

Received on: 20 Jul- 2023

Revised on: 21-Sep-2023

Accepted on: 10 Oct-2023

First Published:30-Dec-2023

Cite this Article as

Ahmad F & Singh D (2023), "A Study About Stressed Assets Management of South Indian Bank", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 11, Issue 2, 2023, pp 01-23. DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.10714581

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This research delves into the pivotal role of the banking sector in economic growth, with a focus on South Indian Bank's financial performance, particularly trends in Gross Advances, Gross Non Performing Assets (NPAs), and asset quality fluctuations from 2019 to 2023. Examining the bank's loan portfolio across sectors and assessing NPAs in priority and non-priority sectors from 2013-14 to 2022-23, the study relies on reliable sources and statistical tools. While valuable for policymakers and investors, it acknowledges limitations like time constraints and secondary data reliance. Despite these, it contributes to NPA management understanding, suggesting risk mitigation strategies for the banking sector and concluding with industry implications and future research recommendations.

Methodology: The research relies on secondary data gathered from sources such as RBI, South Indian Bank websites, and staff members. Annual reports from 2019-2023 serve as the primary data set, extracted through the bank's website, including investor presentations. Limited data availability prompted the use of graphs and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for comparative and analytical purposes.

Findings: The rise in NPAs is influenced by external factors such as global dynamics, pandemics, and economic slowdowns, and internal factors like government policies and inefficient management. Inadequate pre-sanction assessment and post-sanction monitoring, along with delays in identifying wilful defaulters, also contribute. Legal delays, inadequate policies, and macroeconomic factors exacerbate the issue, impacting the economy and causing capital discouragement and reduced bank earnings.

Practical Implications: As the study relies on reliable sources and statistical tools. While valuable for policymakers and investors, it acknowledges limitations like time constraints and secondary data reliance. Despite these, it contributes to NPA management understanding, suggesting risk mitigation strategies for the banking sector and concluding with industry implications and future research recommendations.

Originality/Value: *To confirm the originality of this study, to the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to examine the issues of NPAs of South Indian Bank.*

Keywords: *NPAs, Risk mitigation, Stressed assets Managements*

Paper Type: *Research Paper*

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking industry stands as a cornerstone of any kind of banking structure, playing a pivotal role in ensuring overall economic well-being. By accepting deposits and extending banks and loans effectively generate credit, which is crucial for economic growth. However, the existence of assets that are not performing (NPAs) interferes with this important credit cycle, impeding both credit expansion and bank profitability. NPAs serve as leading indicators of a

Banking sector's performance, reflecting the effectiveness of lending practices. In November 2018, the Indian Reserve Bank (RBI) reported that India's banking structure was burdened with over Rs 9 lakh crores in poor-quality loans, underscoring the detrimental impact on banks' liquidity positions and lending practices. This alarming growth in NPAs over the past five years points to systemic issues in lending practices. (Neha S, & Pathak O.P 2017; Agarwala & Agarwala, 2019)

“SCBs’ gross non-performing assets (GNPA) ratio continued its downtrend and fell to a 10-year low of 3.9 per cent in March 2023 and the net non-performing assets (NNPA) ratio declined to 1.0 per cent.” (Dayal, 2023)

In this context, the South Indian Bank, with its long-standing history dating back to 1929, has increased the scope of its operations and become a significant player in the region of South India banking and financial services landscape. Evaluating its financial performance through various ratios and indicators is essential to gauge its health, profitability, liquidity, and asset quality, which are critical factors in assessing any bank's overall financial well-being. Moreover, the quality of assets in banks and financial institutions serves as a crucial barometer of the broader financial system's health, reflecting credit risk and resource allocation efficiency. However, the deterioration in asset quality, marked by NPAs and stressed assets, it is a question of grave worry for the entire financial sector. (M & Philip, 2023)

Assets- Assets in banking are the financial resources owned or controlled by a bank, including cash, loans, investments, property, and accounts receivable. They are crucial for a bank's financial stability, used to provide services, generate income, and meet obligations.

Stressed assets management- Stressed assets are those that are facing difficulties in generating income or are at risk of defaulting on their obligations, such as loans, advances, or other investments. The primary aim of stressed assets management is to minimize potential losses and maximize recoveries from these distressed assets. It involves various strategies and

actions to rehabilitate or recover the assets and mitigate the impact of non-performing or underperforming loans or investments.

1.1 Types of Stressed Assets:

Special Mention Accounts (SMA): Special Mention Accounts refer to those assets where there is an early sign of stress or potential default. These assets are not yet categorized as underperforming; yet, require close monitoring and proactive action by the bank to prevent them from becoming NPA (Non-Performing Asset).

- i. SMA-0: This category includes accounts where one to thirty days have passed since the principle or interest payment is due. SMA-0 accounts serve as a warning to borrowers that they need to regularize their payments immediately to avoid further consequences.
- ii. SMA-1: Accounts with an overdue period of 31 to 60 days fall under the SMA-1 category. At this stage, banks intensify their monitoring and may engage with the borrower to understand the reasons for the delay and work towards finding a resolution.
- iii. SMA-2: SMA-2 accounts are those where the payments are overdue for 61 to 90 days. At this stage, the risk of the account slipping into the NPA category becomes significant, and banks typically initiate measures to rectify the account and recover dues promptly.

Non-Performing Assets (NPA): NPAs are assets in cases where the debtor has not pay principle or interest for a specific period, typically 90 days (Bank, 2019). NPAs are divided into several categories substandard, shaky, or lose assets because of on the degree of impairment and the likelihood of recovery.

- i. Substandard Assets: These are assets that have been classified as non-performing for a specific period, typically 90 days, but less than 12 months. Substandard assets have a higher risk of default, and their full recovery is doubtful.
- ii. Doubtful Assets: Doubtful assets are those that remained NPA for more than 12 months (RBI).
- iii. Loss Assets: Loss assets are considered irrecoverable, with little or no chance of recovery. These assets are identified as such by the bank, internal auditors, or regulatory authorities. The bank writes off loss assets from its books and fully provisions for the loss.

1.2 Causes for Special Mention accounts (SMA):

- i. Cheques issued by borrowers are frequently returned.
- ii. Bills or cheques discounted by the bank are being returned.
- iii. Bills discounted or under collection are not being paid.
- iv. The financial performance is weak, with declining sales, profits, cash losses, net losses, and a decrease in net worth.
- v. Borrowers are not complying with the terms and conditions of the loan sanction.
- vi. Interest service failure in Working Capital accounts, Term Loans etc.
- vii. Continuous Overdrawing in accounts beyond the sanctioned amount.

- viii. Non-renewal of working capital limits beyond 180 days.
- ix. On-updating of Stock Statements every month.

Mode to tackle SMA is through strict monitoring, giving regular reminder to the customer.

At this stage also provisioning is made for the Special Mention Account (SMA) assets.

Figure1: Classifications of Stressed Assets

Source-Computed by author from RBI website

Any advance or loan that is past due by more than ninety days is classified as a non-performing asset in India by the Reserve Bank of India (about 3 months). “An asset becomes non-performing when it ceases to generate income for the bank,” said RBI in a circular from 2007 (RBI). Non-Performing Assets impact the bank's operations and the nation's inflation and multiplier effect on economic expansion.

Non-performing assets can be divided into two categories (NPA):

Total Assets that Aren't Working (GNPA)- These assets are the total amount of all the loans that the borrowers who obtained loans from the financial institution have defaulted on.

Net Assets That Are Not Performing (NNPA)- NNPA represents non-performing assets after deducting bank provisions, showing the actual value of defaulted loans

1.3 NPA Classifications / Causes

- i. **Renewal expiry of Operative accounts**- If an account is not renewed within 180 days from original sanction expiry, account will be categorized as NPA.
- ii. **Continuously overdrawn**: If the outstanding in the account is continuously overdrawn for 90 days (for agricultural loans 365 days) prior to the quarter end date, compared to Limit or DP whichever is lower, account will be classified as NPA.
- iii. **Minimum Credit compared to Interest Debit**: Remittance if it's insufficient to pay the interest that was deducted throughout the quarter.

- iv. No Credit: If the account has no credit transaction continuously for 90 days prior to the quarter end date, account will be classified as NPA.
- v. Ad-hoc limits/TOD: If such a limit is not regularized within 180 days from sanction date or 90 days from expiry of ad hoc-limit whichever is earlier, The account will be categorized as NPA.
- vi. Term Loans- If either principal, interest or charges are not paid within 90 days from the demand date, accounts will be classified as NPA.

Table 1: Types of Assets and its provisions

Types of assets	Provisions
Standard Assets	0.25% for all types of Standard Advances
Sub-Standard Assets	A general provision of 10% of the outstanding;
Doubtful Assets	
- Up to One Year	100%-unsecured Advances, 20%-secured Advances
- One to three Year	100%-unsecured Advances, 30%-secured Advances
-more than three Year	100%-unsecured Advances, 100%-secured Advances
Loss Assets	100%-unsecuredAdvances, 100%-secured Advances

Source- www.rbi.org.in

Modes to tackle NPAs

- i. SARFAESI Act - Enacted in 2002, the SARFAESI Act enhances debt recovery efficiency by empowering banks to swiftly seize and sell securities, expediting loan recovery and mitigating Non-Performing Assets, fostering financial health.
- ii. IBC-The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC) of 2016 streamlines insolvency resolution for companies and individuals, ensuring a time-bound, creditor-friendly process to maximize distressed asset value and promote economic growth.
- iii. DRT- The Bank and Financial Institutions Recovery of Debts Act, 1993 (RDDBFI Act) Established by the DRT Act, Debt Recovery Tribunals (DRT) and Appellate Tribunals (DRAT) swiftly adjudicate and recover debts for banks and financial institutions, addressing borrower grievances and handling appeals. However, challenges include a slow resolution process, with approximately 93,000 pending cases in 2016. The World Bank noted prolonged insolvency resolution in India compared to similar economies like China (Dey,2018).The establishment of 39 DRTs and 5 DRATs as single Member Tribunals has not fully addressed the problem of backlog.
- iv. Suit file-Lenders pursue legal action against defaulting borrowers in civil court, presenting loan agreements and evidence of default to obtain a judgment for asset seizure and debt settlement.
- v. Negotiation-Negotiation offers a vital alternative to legal action for resolving debt issues. Lender and borrower discussions aim for mutually beneficial solutions, such as loan restructuring, settlements, or extended repayment, fostering amicable resolutions and preserving relationships.
- vi. Write-offs- A loan that has been written off is deemed to be disposed of. It is applied to cases of non-performing assets (NPA) or substandard loans.

1.4 Legal proceedings after an account are classified as NPA (in case of secured loans)

Figure 2:Legal proceedings after an account are classified as NPA (in case of secured loans)
 Source- Computed by author from RBI website(www.rbi.org.in)

1.5 Legal proceedings after an account are classified as NPA (in case of unsecured loans)

Figure 3:Legal proceedings after an account are classified as NPA (in case of unsecured loans) Source- Computed by author

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kaushik & Kumar, (2023) aimed to assess the efficiency of recovery routes for assets that are not performing (NPAs) in Indian banks, exploring mechanisms like SARFAESI Act, Lok Adalat’s, DRTs, and IBC. Utilizing secondary data from 2016 to 2022, the research employed ANOVA and multiple comparisons. Findings indicated significant differences among recovery channels, with IBC showing superior efficacy. The study concludes that enhancing recovery management practices, particularly through IBC, can substantially improve NPA resolution for Indian banks.

(M & Philip, 2023) This study delves into South Indian Bank's financial health, examining profitability, solvency, deposit and advance growth, and deposit mix from 2016-17 to 2020-21. Utilizing ratio analysis, it reveals a consistent increase in deposits and advances, highlights a need for increased lending, and suggests focusing on term deposits. Despite challenges from the pandemic, the bank addresses issues, emphasizing digitalization and improving asset quality. The study draws conclusions based on the fiscal year 2021 and recommends enhancing customer outreach for market expansion.

(Vibhute, Jewargi, & Haralayya, 2021) Efficiency and NPAs share a negative correlation in India's banking evolution from pre-independence (1786–1947) to post-liberalization (1991–present). Bank failures pre-independence resulted from infrastructure gaps, mismanagement, fraud, and human error. Nationalization of 14 banks occurred in 1969. Post-1991 economic reforms allowed 10 private banks in India, and international banks established offices, marking the end of bank nationalization. The composition of NPAs in Priority and non-priority sectors are involved with public sector banks., with higher NPAs in the latter but failed to explained this.

(Agarwala & Agarwala, 2019) This research addresses a critical gap by focusing on individual banks' non-performing assets (NPAs) post-2017, diverging from the group-centric approach. Private banks, including Axis, Yes, and ICICI, experience increasing NPAs, possibly tied to the 2015 RBI asset quality review. DCB excels in NPA management, while SBI displays mixed results. Nationalized banks like Punjab National and Andhra grapple with persistent NPA challenges despite marginal improvement in 2016-2017. The study underscores the pressing need for concerted efforts to curb NPA growth, vital for overall economic growth and bank stability.

(Rana, 2019) This study delves into Non-Operating Resources (NPAs) within the banking industry, focusing on impact, identification, and management. It highlights causes, internal checks, and management strategies, noting public sector banks' NPA issues stem from social objectives and credit assessment shortcomings. Recommendations include enhanced risk management, reduced political influence, and the need for quantitative analysis and post-September 2021 updates. The findings underscore NPAs' adverse effects, advocating early warning systems, compromise settlements, timely responses, and unified approaches. The study calls for further empirical investigations into resolution effectiveness amid regulatory changes.

Rathore, Malpani, & Sharma, (2016) Studied the Indian scheduled commercial banks' non-performing assets (NPAs) in terms of stressed assets, gross NPAs and net NPAs and stressed assets are quite high and its negative impact on banks' profitability, liability management and loss of investors' confidence. The various channels through which NPAs can be recovered, Lok Adalat and the scrutinization act also one can adopt for compromise proposals. The finding of this paper is that there is a negative relationship between NPA Bank, Net Profits, and Total Advances.

Biswas, (2014) evaluates assets that are not performing (NPAs) in slated financial institutions, analyzing gross and net NPAs, loan asset classification, and proposing management strategies. Despite a data gap in 2014, it identifies a concerning upward trend in NPAs since 2008, emphasizing the need for stringent loan approval criteria, technological integration, regulatory compliance, and adaptive policymaking for effective recovery systems. The study underscores the importance of preserving asset value and job protection while addressing mismanagement or fraud.

(Saluja & Lal, 2010) They analysed the NPA growth has a significant impact on substandard loans as lending rates rise, NPA increases and decrease in the growth of industrial credit as a result of the buildup of NPAs which led to the decline in the industrial sector from 2009 till 2017. He proposed that for recapitalisation of affected banks to solve the current level of accumulation.

(Rajender, 2009) Examining the performance of other portfolios, and decision-making processes in the field of NPA management in public sector banks, emphasising asset quality, various statistical tools are used like ANOVA test correlation to understand NPAs' effect on profitability and solvency of the banks in the public sector. Asset-wise classification has an extremely strong negative connection between performing and non-performing assets. Also, there is an extremely strong negative connection in another sector of the priority sector.

3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Gross NPA of Large Corporate borrowers are higher than the retail borrowers like Retail and MSMEs, though not much research has been done in this dimension as how the recovery team deal with these NPAs .

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- i. To study the trends of Gross Non-Performing Assets, Gross Advances and Gross Advances Compared to Gross NPA (%) (2019-2023)
- ii. To examine the trends of Substandard Assets, Questionable 1, Questionable 2, Questionable 3, and Loss Assets. To examine if Business loans exhibit a higher Gross NPA than other loan categories from 2021 to 2023.
- iii. To analyse the NPA trends in Priority and Non-Priority sectors from 2013-14 to 2022-23

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The research relies on secondary data gathered from sources such as RBI, South Indian Bank websites, and staff members. Annual reports from 2019-2023 serve as the primary data set, extracted through the bank's website, including investor presentations. Limited data availability prompted the use of graphs and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for comparative and analytical purposes.

5. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Performance Evaluation Of South Indian Bank

To research the trends of Gross Advances, Gross Non-Performing Assets, and Gross NPA to Gross advances (%) from 2019-2023.

To have a clear picture of the analysis, we have taken the data from 2019 to 2023 of Gross Advances, Gross Non-Performing Assets, and Gross NPA to Gross Advances of South Indian Bank.

Table 2: Gross NPA, Gross Advances and Gross NPA to Gross Advances (%) (in crores)

Year	Gross Advances	Gross NPA	Gross NPAs to Gross Advances Ratio (%)
2019	63636	3131.67	4.92
2020	65524	3261.77	4.98
2021	59418	4143.24	6.97
2022	61816	3648.09	5.9
2023	72092	3708	5.14
CAGR	0.025266672	0.034362451	0.008787293

Source- Computed by author from South Indian Bank and RBI website

FIGURE 4: Gross NPA, Gross Advances and Gross NPA to Gross Advances(%)

Source-(Computed using RBI data and South Indian Bank) (South Indian Bank)

Figure 4 Shows Gross advances have shown an increasing trend from 2019 to 2023. In 2021, the gross advances were relatively low, at Rs. 59,418 crores. However, in the most recent year, 2023, the gross advances reached their highest level in the last five years, reaching Rs. 72,092 crores. In 2021, the Gross NPA was the highest at Rs. 4,143.24 crores, whereas in 2023, it decreased to Rs. 3,708 crores. However, it still remains higher than the pre-COVID level. Regarding the Gross NPA to gross advances ratio, we can observe an increasing trend from 2019 to 2021. In 2021, it reached its peak but gradually reduced to 5.14% in 2023. Nevertheless, it is still higher than the pre-COVID level of 4.92%. The CAGR for gross advances stands at 0.025, and for Gross NPA, it is 0.034. Gross NPA to Gross Advances Ratio is 0.008.

5.2 To examine the trends of Substandard Assets, Doubtful 1, Doubtful 2, Doubtful 3 and loss Assets.

We will analyze the historical patterns and developments in Substandard Assets, Doubtful 1, Doubtful 2, Doubtful 3, and Loss Assets, spanning from the fiscal year 2013-14 through 2022-23.

Table3: (Trends of Substandard Assets, Doubtful 1, Doubtful 2, Doubtful 3 and loss Assets) (in Millions)

Year/Amount	Substandard	Doubtful-I	Doubtful-2	Doubtful-3	Loss
2013-14	1,798.08	1,963.07	54.95	28.27	481.85
2014-15	2136.25	1699.56	2067.62	92.33	438.74
2015-16	9,066.24	5,260.67	1,107.79	32.88	156.04
2016-17	5,294.33	2,343.99	3,585.59	96.49	169.66
2017-18	12,354.70	2,614.20	4,354.70	164.9	314.5
2018-19	14,455.07	9,782.88	6,189.96	464.92	423.9
2019-20	11,136.52	10,962.48	10,006.66	73.52	438.48
2020-21	22,453.76	4,170.73	13,662.28	828.54	317.11
2021-22	13,504.80	12,149.70	6,767.45	3,334.58	724.41
2022-23	7,122.73	10,302.30	12,587.41	5,588.73	1,481.48

Source- Computed by author using South Indian Bank website (South Indian Bank)

Figure 5: Trends of Substandard Assets, Doubtful 1, Doubtful 2, Doubtful 3 and loss Assets (in Millions Rs.)

Source- Computed by author using RBI data and South Indian Bank

These categories represent the classification of assets based on their credit quality. Here's a breakdown of the data and its interpretation:

- i. Substandard: The highest recorded amount for Substandard assets was in the year 2020-21 at Rs. 22,453.76 million. This category shows a general trend of increase from 2013-14 to 2020-21, indicating deteriorating asset quality. After 2020-21, there has been a decline in Substandard assets, reaching Rs. 7,122.73 million in 2022-23, which could indicate an improvement in asset quality.
- ii. Doubtful-I: The highest recorded amount for Doubtful-I assets was in the year 2021-22 at Rs. 12,149.70 million. There is a significant increase in Doubtful-I assets from 2013-14 to 2019-20, followed by a decrease in 2020-21 and a subsequent increase in 2021-22. In 2022-23, Doubtful-I assets decreased to Rs. 10,302.30 million.
- iii. Doubtful-2: The highest recorded amount for Doubtful-2 assets was in the year 2020-21 at Rs. 13,662.28 million. Doubtful-2 assets show fluctuations over the years, with a peak in 2020-21 and a decrease in 2022-23 to Rs. 12,587.41 million.
- iv. Doubtful-3: The highest recorded amount for Doubtful-3 assets was in the year 2022-23 at Rs. 5,588.73 million. Doubtful-3 assets have increased consistently over the years, suggesting a rising trend of assets at high risk of default.
- v. Loss: The highest recorded amount for Loss assets was in the year 2022-23 at Rs. 1,481.48 million. Loss assets also show fluctuations, with a spike in 2019-20 followed by a decrease in 2020-21. In 2022-23, Loss assets increased to Rs. 1,481.48 million.

Overall, the bank should closely monitor its Doubtful-3 and Loss assets to prevent further deterioration in asset quality, while efforts to reduce Substandard and Doubtful-I assets seem to be showing some positive results.

Reasons for fluctuations

The performance of a bank over several financial years, highlighting fluctuations in Total Assets Non-Performing (GNPA) and Net Non-Performing Assets (Net NPA) along with the reasons for these fluctuations.

2013-14: The bank experienced a decline in GNPA from Rs. 433.87 crore to Rs. 432.62 crore. This was attributed to NPA recovery and one-time compromise settlements.

2015-16: GNPA increased significantly to Rs.1,562.36 crore. This was attributed to a substantial fresh slippage of Rs. 1,342.52 crore in the corporate sector, offsetting recovery efforts.

2016-17: GNPA decreased to Rs. 1,149.01 crore due to effective recovery measures and asset sales to Asset Reconstruction Companies (ARCs).

2017-18: GNPA rose again to Rs. 1,980.30 crore, mainly due to fresh slippages of Rs. 614.00 crore from the corporate sector, despite recovery efforts.

2018-19: GNPA increased to Rs. 3,131.67 crore, primarily due to slippages from legacy corporate accounts.

2019-20: Recovery efforts reduced Net NPA, but GNPA remained high at Rs. 3,261.77 crore due to corporate sector slippages.

2020-21: GNPA increased to Rs. 4,143.24 crore due to the impact of COVID-19, resulting in slippages from corporate and retail sectors.

2021-22: Recovery efforts led to a decline in GNPA to Rs.3,648.09 crore, despite the pandemic's effects.

2022-23: Strong recovery efforts resulted in a significant decrease in GNPA to Rs.1,513.22 crore.

Overall, fluctuations in GNPA were primarily driven by factors such as fresh slippages, corporate sector challenges, and the COVID-19 pandemic's effects. The bank's focused and sustained efforts in recovery, asset sales, credit underwriting, and due diligence played a crucial role in mitigating these fluctuations and improving asset quality over time. The bank's performance improved as it learned from past challenges and adapted its strategies to address them effectively. (South Indian Bank)

5.3 To examine if Business loans exhibit a higher Gross NPA than other loan categories from 2021 to 2023

While the interest rates on personal loans tend to be relatively higher when compared to corporate or business loans, it is essential to examine the all assets that are not performing (NPAs) in the business sector. Here other loan types include personal loans and agricultural loans.

Table 4: Corporate Segment (in Rs. crores)

Year	Corporate lending	Corporate GNPA
2021	14721	1585
2022	16925	609
2023	23523	741
CAGR	0.169100372	-0.22387862

Source- Computed by author using South Indian Bank website

FIGURE 6: Corporate Segment (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed by author using Data from South Indian Bank website

Corporate lending is showing an increasing trend from 2021 to 2023. In 2021, it amounted to Rs. 14,721 crores, while in 2023, it reached Rs. 23,523 crores. Additionally, the corporate gross NPA decreased from Rs. 1,585 crores in 2021 to Rs. 741 crores in 2023, despite the lending being at its highest. The reason for higher GNPA in 2021 can be attributed due to COVID-19 effects.

Table5: Personal Segment (in Rs Crores)

Year	Personal segment lending	Personal segment GNPA
2021	14818	478
2022	14612	510
2023	16153	481
CAGR	0.029171776	0.002087689

Source- Computed by author using South Indian Bank website

FIGURE 7: Personal Segment (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed using Data from South Indian Bank website

Personal segment lending was Rs.14,818 crores in 2021, Rs.14,612 crores in 2022, and Rs.16,153 crores in 2023. Overall, the personal segment lending shows an increasing trend, but it experienced a decline in 2022. In 2022, the gross NPA reached its highest level at Rs. 510 crores, while in 2023, it decreased slightly to Rs. 481 crores, but it still remains higher than the Rs. 478 crores recorded in 2021.

The reason for higher GNPA in 2022 can be attributed due to COVID-19 effects, high provisioning and unsecured loans.

Table 6: Business Segment (in Rs. Crores)

Year	Business Segment lending	Business Segment GNPA
2021	19456	1710
2022	18349	1993
2023	18350	1938
CAGR	-0.019319582	0.042603601

Source- Computed by author using South Indian Bank website

FIGURE 8: Business Segment (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed using Data from South Indian Bank website

Business lending in 2021 was Rs. 19,456 crores, whereas in 2023, it decreased to Rs. 18,350 crores. The highest business lending was recorded in 2021, while the lowest was in 2022. Business segment GNPA, it reached its highest value in 2022, at Rs. 1,993, and its lowest value in 2021, at Rs. 1,710. However, in the last year, it increased to Rs. 1,930.

The reason for higher GNPA in 2021 can be attributed due to COVID-19 effects, exposure to high risks, and high provisioning.

Table 7: Agricultural Segment

Year	Agriculture lending	Agriculture GNPA
2021	10423	370
2022	11930	536
2023	14066	548
CAGR	0.105077216	0.139881254

Source- Computed by author using South Indian Bank website

FIGURE 9: Agricultural Segment (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed by author using Data from South Indian Bank website

Agricultural lending shows an increasing trend from 2021 to 2023, rising from Rs. 10,423 crores to Rs. 14,066 crores. Similarly, agricultural GNPA is also on the rise, increasing from Rs. 370 crores in 2021 to Rs. 548 crores in 2023. Therefore, both agricultural lending and agricultural GNPA exhibit an increasing trend.

The reason for higher agricultural lending and agricultural GNPA can be attributed due to COVID-19 effects and government policies.

TABLE 8: Lending and GNPA of Composition of loan book (amount in Rs. crores)

Year	Corporate lending	Corporate GNPA
2021	14721	1585
2022	16925	609
2023	23523	741
CAGR	0.1691	-0.22388
SUM	55169	2935
Year	Personal segment lending	Personal segment GNPA
2021	14818	478
2022	14612	510
2023	16153	481
CAGR	0.029172	0.002088
SUM	45583	1469
Year	Business Segment lending	Business Segment GNPA

2021	19456	1710
2022	18349	1993
2023	18350	1938
CAGR	-0.01932	0.042604
SUM	56155	5641
Year	Agriculture lending	Agriculture GNPA
2021	10423	370
2022	11930	536
2023	14066	548
CAGR	0.105077	0.139881
SUM	36419	1454

Source- Computed by author using Data from South Indian Bank website)

In the past three years, corporate sector lending totalled Rs. 55,169 crores with a GNPA of Rs. 2,935 crores, exhibiting a slight lending increase (CAGR 0.16), but a negative GNPA CAGR (-0.22). Business segment lending was Rs. 56,155 crores with a GNPA of Rs. 5,641 crores, showing a slight lending decrease (CAGR -0.019) and a positive GNPA CAGR (0.04). Personal lending amounted to Rs. 45,583 crores with a GNPA of Rs. 1,469 crores, featuring a CAGR of 0.02 and NPAs at 0.002. Agricultural lending reached Rs. 36,419 crores with a GNPA of Rs. 1,454 crores, displaying a lending CAGR of 0.10 and a GNPA CAGR of 0.13 over the period

FIGURE 10: Comparison of business loan and other types of loans (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed by author using Data from South Indian Bank website

We can observe that Corporate and Business Segment lending is higher than Personal and agricultural lending Throughout the past three years, that is from 2021 to 2023. In 2023 Corporate and Business segment lending was Rs. 41,873 crores and Personal and agricultural segment was Rs. 30,219 crores. In 2023 Corporate and Business segment GNPA was Rs. 2,679 crores and Personal and agricultural segment was Rs. 1,029 crores. Despite secured assets in the corporate sector, it faces higher NPAs .

According to the RBI, the proportion of the top 100 major borrowers for the entire amount of the loan portfolio of Commercial Banks Scheduled (SCBs) continued to increase, reaching 17.4% by September 2022. This suggests that large corporate entities have been engaging in new borrowing activities. However, it is noteworthy that Additionally, these top 100 borrowers' asset quality displayed improvement. Their proportion of SCBs' Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPA) dropped from 6.8% in March 2022 to 5.4% in September 2022. (mint)

5.4 To analyze the NPA trends in Priority and Non-Priority sectors from 2013-14 to 2022-23

The analysis concerning Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) is a critical endeavour for financial institutions, providing insights into the health and risk profile of their lending portfolios. This research explores the NPA trends in sectors that are both priority and non-priority from the fiscal year 2013-14 to 2022-23. The Priority Sector, encompassing vital segments like Activities related to agriculture, advances to businesses qualified for priority sector financing, Textile, Basic Metal, Infrastructure, Services, Professional-Trade, Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs), Personal loans, Housing Loans, and Other Personal loans, including Gold Loans, plays a pivotal role in fostering economic development. On the other hand, the Sector That Is Not Priority, which includes Industry, agriculture, and related fields (Textile, Basic Metal, Infra), Services (Professional, Trade), NBFCs, and various personal loan categories, also contributes significantly to the financial landscape. Understanding the NPA dynamics in these sectors is crucial for formulating effective risk management strategies and sustaining a healthy financial ecosystem.

TABLE 9: Priority Sector and Non-Priority Sector

Year	Priority Sector			Non Priority Sector		
	Outstanding Total Advances	Gross NPAs	Percentage of Gross NPAs to Total Advances in that sector	Outstanding Total Advances	Gross NPAs	Percentage of Gross NPAs to Total Advances in that sector
2013-14	11499.36	120.51	1.05%	24903.73	312.11	1.25%
2014-15	13289.27	189.03	1.42%	24436.4	454.41	1.86%
2015-16	16362.96	297.39	1.82%	25107.83	1264.97	5.04%
2016-17	19,047.71	470.71	2.47%	27,797.97	678.3	2.44%
2017-18	22,794.32	716.7	3.14%	32,314.68	1,263.60	3.91%
2018-19	25,365.98	1,221.83	4.82%	38,269.94	1,909.84	4.99%
2019-20	27748.09	1271.51	4.58%	37775.96	1990.25	5.27%
2020-21	32,081.35	2,373.70	7.40%	27,337.05	1,769.54	6.47%
2021-22	30,831.46	2,464.05	7.99%	30,984.30	1,184.04	3.82%
2022-23	30,582.38	1,912.23	6.25%	41,509.68	1,796.03	4.33%

Source- Computed by author using Data from RBI and South Indian Bank website

FIGURE 11: Priority Sector and Non-Priority Sector

Source-

Computed by author using Data from South Indian Bank annual reports.

The Priority Sector, encompassing vital economic areas like agriculture and education, had a low NPA percentage of 1.05% in 2013-14. However, it increased, peaking at 4.82% in 2018-19, with subsequent fluctuations, reaching 6.25% in 2022-23. Loans to the Non-Priority Sector, including large industries, had a 1.25% NPA percentage in 2013-14, slightly higher than the Priority Sector. It increased, peaking at 6.47% in 2020-21, then decreased to 4.33% in 2022-23.

NPA percentages in the sectors of priority and non-priority increased consistently, notably in 2020-21 due to global economic challenges. Effective risk management is crucial for mitigating impact

FIGURE 12: Recoveries (in Rs. Crores)

Source- Computed using Data from South Indian Bank website

It is evident that the recovery trend has been consistently increasing from the year 2020 to 2023. The recovery amount was Rs. 530 crores in 2020 and significantly escalated to Rs.1,814 crores in 2023.

Notably, there was a remarkable surge in recoveries between 2021 and 2022, jumping from Rs.690 crores to Rs.1,464 crores.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the recovery amount during this period is calculated at 0.36. Moreover, 2023 witnessed the highest recovery amount of Rs.1,814 crores.

Accountant and unaccounted money during NPAs auction pose a major hurdle; only accounted funds are accepted.

South Indian Bank employs diverse methods for loan recovery, including the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC), SARFAESI Act, write-offs, one-time settlements, Debt Recovery Tribunal (DRT) proceedings, and initiating legal suits. These multifaceted approaches enable the bank to address loan recovery comprehensively and navigate diverse scenarios efficiently.

5.5 Distinct reasons for the increase in NPAs .

There can be various impacts of NPAs on the growth of the economy as it discourages capital formation, reduces earning capacity of the banks also creates a twin balance sheet problem. (Sikdar, 2020)

FIGURE 13: Reasons for NPA

Source- Computed by Author

The primary cause is the overestimation of economic growth, which forces the banking sector to competently provide loans during the peak of the business cycle. (Mukhopadhyay, 2018)

(i) Funds being diverted for purposes such as expansion, modernization, initiating new projects, or supporting sister concerns.(Secretariat, 2022)

(ii) Delays and increased costs experienced during project implementation.

Instances of wilful default, diversion of funds, fraudulent activities, misappropriation, disputes between promoters or management, and related issues. (secretariat, 2014)

Increasing operational independence in the commercial banking sector was the primary goal of the Narasimha Committee in 1991. It recommended measures such as lowering the cash reserve ratio and the statutory liquidity ratio, which would lessen the pre-emption of banks' investible resources, and eventually eliminating the administered interest rate structure. The Narasimha Committee recommended in 1998 that the banking sector take more measures to modernize, including adopting prudential rules and enhancing regulation and supervision. It also promoted a review of the ownership structure of Indian banks. (Mohan & Ray, 2017)

5.6 Impact of NPAs on Indian Banking Sectors

- i. Financial Losses- NPAs lead to bank losses, impacting profitability and financial stability due to failure in recovering principal and interest.
- ii. Capital Adequacy- Provisions for bad loans reduce capital reserves, limiting lending capacity.
- iii. Liquidity Concerns- High NPAs cause liquidity problems; banks struggle with daily tasks like withdrawals and honouring lending commitments.
- iv. Restructuring and Recovery Efforts- Legal action, loan restructuring, and asset recovery divert funds from profitable operations, impacting the bank's finances.
- v. Twin Balance sheet problem to four balance sheet problem (NPA's in India, 2022) (Secretariat, 2022) (Khandelwal & Sharan, 2022).

5.7 Effect of Digitalization on NPA in Indian Bank

Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in India have been significantly impacted by digitalization. Loans or advances that are considered NPAs are those where the borrowers have been unable to make payments for a predetermined amount of time, usually 90 days. Here are a few examples of how digitization has affected NPAs in India

- i. Credit Evaluation Process Improvement
- ii. Improved Monitoring and Early Warning Systems
- iii. Loan Disbursement Procedure Simplified
- iv. Strengthened Fraud Detection

In conclusion, the analysis underscores the dynamic nature of NPAs influenced by various external and internal factors. Effective risk management, recovery strategies, and the transformative impact of digitalization are imperative for banks to navigate the complex landscape of non-performing assets.

6. FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

- i. Gross advances peaked at Rs.72,092 crores in 2023. Gross NPA fluctuated, decreasing to Rs.3,708 crores in 2023. The Gross NPA to gross advances ratio rose to 6.97% in 2021, decreased to 5.14% in 2023.
- ii. Substandard assets peaked in 2018-19, reduced to Rs. 7,122.73 million by 2022-23.
- iii. Corporate lending rose to Rs. 23,523 crores in 2023; GNPA decreased, possibly due to COVID-19.
- iv. Personal segment lending increased but declined in 2022; personal GNPA decreased slightly in 2023.
- v. Business segment lending peaked in 2021; business GNPA decreased from 2022 to 2023.
- vi. Agricultural lending and GNPA increased from 2021 to 2023.
- vii. Corporate and Business Segment lending exceeded Personal and Agricultural lending in 2023.
- viii. NPA percentage in Priority Sector declined to 6.25% in 2022-23.
- ix. Non-Priority Sector NPA decreased to 4.33% in 2022-23.

- x. Recovery trends increased, with 2023 recording the highest recovery amount of Rs.1,814 crores.
- xi. MSME sector lending showed a slight decrease; GNPA had a positive CAGR despite the lending decline.
- xii. Personal lending had a positive CAGR for GNPA despite a slight increase in lending; agricultural lending showed positive CAGRs.
- xiii. The primary factor for rising GNPA at South Indian Bank is the impact of COVID-19.
- xiv. The rise in NPAs is influenced by external factors such as global dynamics, pandemics, and economic slowdowns, and internal factors like government policies and inefficient management. Inadequate pre-sanction assessment and post-sanction monitoring, along with delays in identifying wilful defaulters, also contribute. Legal delays, inadequate policies, and macroeconomic factors exacerbate the issue, impacting the economy and causing capital discouragement and reduced bank earnings.

The Narasimha Committee in 1991 sought to provide the commercial banking sector more operational flexibility and recommended actions to modernize the financial sector through enhanced oversight and regulation.

NPAs impact the banking sector through financial losses, reduced capital adequacy, liquidity concerns, restructuring efforts, and twin balance sheet problems.

The bank addressed challenges by emphasizing digitalization and enhancing asset quality through reduced exposure to stressed sectors. (M & Philip, 2023)

PCR (including write off) improved by 1805 bps from 58.73% as at Mar 2021 to 76.78% March 2022. (South Indian Bank)

The banking sector analysis spanning 2019 to 2023 underscores a resilient growth in gross advances despite challenges. Substantial improvement in substandard assets and recovery efforts reduced GNPA. Corporate lending saw growth with diminishing NPAs, while challenges persist, emphasizing the need for robust risk management, recovery strategies, and proactive policy measures for financial stability. In conclusion, effectively addressing Non-performing assets include crucial for financial steadiness and economic health. The study recommends strategic measures, adaptive policies, and technological advancements to fortify the banking sector, emphasizing the dynamic nature of NPAs as well as the necessity of efficient risk management and digitalization

To curb In order to better manage Non-Performing Assets (NPAs), the bank must credit appraisal system. When NPAs occur, effective resolution depends on a supportive legal framework. Recovery, especially for stock loans, often involves lengthy legal proceedings in India, causing significant delays despite the bank's efforts. Obtaining court permission for physical possession of properties, a vital step in the recovery process, takes a minimum of one to two years (Mishra & Pawaskar, 2017).

The South Indian Bank has demonstrated effective management of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs). The institution efficiently extends loans to individuals capable of repaying, enabling them to proactively handle NPA accounts through successful loan recovery measures. (R.Priyadharshini, 2018)

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Managing non-performing assets is vital for the well-being of a financial institution. Here are some proposed solutions:

- i. Enhancing credit assessment within risk management to prevent the emergence of new NPAs
- ii. Promoting flexible negotiations between banks and borrowers to effectively address NPAs
- iii. Establishing interconnections among banks to access customers' credit histories, aiding in informed loan approvals.
- iv. Conducting regular surveys like Asset Quality Reviews.
- v. Employing Artificial Intelligence to bolster the banking system's strength.
- vi. Use of Artificial Intelligence to strengthen the Banking system
- vii. Special law should be made to avoid cronyism
- viii. Competent employees

REFERENCES

- Agarwala, V., & Agarwala, N. (2019). A critical review of non-performing assets in the Indian banking industry. *Rajagiri Management Journal*, 13(2), 12-23. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/RAMJ-08-2019-0010>
- Bank, B. (2019). STRESSED ASSET MANAGEMENT & RECOVERY POLICY (SAMRP). Retrieved from https://www.bandhanbank.com/sites/default/files/2021-08/SAMR_Policy_Final-Version_Board_Approved_10062021.pdf
- Biswas, D. (2014, 12). NON PERFORMING ASSETS OF SCHEDULE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDIA: A STUDY. *Abhinav National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, 3(12), 16-20. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372861090_NON_PERFORMING_ASSETS_OF_SCHEDULE_COMMERCIAL_BANKS_IN_INDIA_A_STUDY
- Dayal, Y. (2023, June 28). Financial Stability Report. Retrieved from <https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/PressRelease/PDFs/PR493FSR27F6AB0B5CEA4F9AA39688FFC08B8D32.PDF>
- Dey, S. (2018, July). Recovery Mechanisms of Non-Performing Assets in Indian Commercial Banks: An Empirical Study. *A multidisciplinary Online Journal of Netaji Subhas Open University, INDIA*, 2(2). Retrieved from <http://www.wbnsou.ac.in/openjournals/Issue/2nd-Issue/Surojit.pdf>
- Kaushik, M., & Kumar, D. (2023). An Empirical Investigation of the Relationship between Recovery Management Practices and Npa Levels In Indian Banks. *Journal of Namibian Studies*, 33(3), 1944-1963. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.59670/jns.v33i.2281>
- Khandelwal, M., & Sharan, D. (2022). NPA's in India. *Parliament, Library and reference, research, documentation and information service (LARRDIS)*, 3-17. Retrieved from https://parliamentlibraryindia.nic.in/lcwing/NPAs_%20in%20india.pdf
- M, P., & Philip, B. (2023). A Study on The Financial Performance of The South Indian Bank. *PriMera Scientific Engineering*, 2(5), 2-13. Retrieved from <https://primerascientific.com/pdf/psen/PSEN-02-049.pdf>
- mint. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/banks-gross-npa-drops-to-7-year-low-at-5-net-npa-at-a-decade-low-rbi-s-fsr-11672318983978.html>

- Mishra, D. M., & Pawaskar, J. R. (2017, March). A Study of Non-Performing Assets and its Impact on Banking Sector. *Journal for Research*, 03(01). Retrieved from <http://www.journal4research.org/articles/J4RV3I1007.pdf>
- Mohan, R., & Ray, P. (2017). Indian Financial Sector: Structure, Trends, and Turns. IMF Working Papers, 5-16. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781475570168.001>
- Mukhopadhyay, A. (2018). Finding Innovative Solutions to India's NPA Woes. ORF ISSUE BRIEF(246), 12. Retrieved from https://www.orfonline.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/ORF_IssueBrief_246_NPAs_FinalForUpload.pdf
- Neha S, & Pathak O.P (2017) "A Comprehensive Review Of Literature Of Micro And Tiny Finance With The Help Of MFIs And SHGs In India", *International Journal of Social Sciences & Economic Environment*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, Jul-Dec, 2017, pp05-12, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53882/IJSSEE.2017.0202002>
- NPA's in India. (2022). PARLIAMENT LIBRARY AND REFERENCE, RESEARCH, DOCUMENTATION AND INFORMATION SERVICE (LARRDIS). Retrieved from https://parliamentlibraryindia.nic.in/lcwing/NPAs_%20in%20India.pdf
- R.Priyadharshini. (2018, February). A STUDY ON EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF NPA IN SOUTH INDIAN BANK. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*, 7(2), 15-20. Retrieved from [https://www.worldwidejournals.com/international-journal-of-scientific-research-\(IJSR\)/fileview.php?val=February_2018_1517574232_199.pdf](https://www.worldwidejournals.com/international-journal-of-scientific-research-(IJSR)/fileview.php?val=February_2018_1517574232_199.pdf)
- Rajender, K. (2009). Management of non performing assets in public sector banks. *The Indian Journal of Commerce*, 62(1), 45-54. Retrieved from <http://icaindia.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Indian-Journal-of-Commerce-January-March-2009.pdf#page=51>
- Rana, C. (2019, May). A Study on Management of Non-Performing Assets in Context of Indian Banking System. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 8(5), 73-77. Retrieved from <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v8i5/ART20197502.pdf>
- Rathore, P., Malpani, D., & Sharma, S. (2016). Non Performing Assets of Indian Banking System and its Impact on Economy. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 7(6), 21-26. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.9790/5933-0706032126>
- Saluja, M. R., & Lal, D. R. (2010). Comparative Analysis on Non performing Assets of public sector, private sector and Foreign Banks in India. *International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management.*, 1(7), 80-88. Retrieved from <https://www.ijrcm.org.in/>
- secretariat, l. s. (2014). Non-Performing Assets and public Sector Banks in India. *PARLIAMENT LIBRARY AND REFERENCE, RESEARCH, DOCUMENTATION*, 2-3. Retrieved from https://loksabhadocs.nic.in/Refinput/New_Reference_Notes/English/Non-Performing.pdf
- Secretariat, L. S. (2022). NPA's,s in India. Retrieved from https://parliamentlibraryindia.nic.in/lcwing/NPAs_%20in%20India.pdf
- Sikdar, A. (2020). NPAs and its effects on banks' profitability. *THE TIMES OF INDIA*. Retrieved from https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/economic-update/NPAs_-and-its-effects-on-banks-profitability/

South Indian Bank. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.southindianbank.com/>

Vibhute, N. s., Jewargi, D. b., & Haralayya, D. (2021). Study on nonperforming assets of public sector banks. SSRN Electronic Journal, 4(12), 52-61. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352399977_Study_on_Non_Performing_Assets_of_Public_Sector_Banks